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Atrial Fibrillation Integrated Approach In Frail, Multimorbid, And Polymedicated Older People

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Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Introduction.....	4
3	MoSCoW prioritisation	5
3.1	Prioritisation	5
3.1.1	Must have	5
3.1.2	Should have	5
3.1.3	Could have	5
3.1.4	Won't have	5
3.2	Refining requirements.....	6
3.3	Determining software output	6
4	High-level requirements.....	7
5	Data model	8
5.1	Field specification.....	8
6	iABC platform requirements	11
7	Security.....	17
7.1	Vulnerability scans.....	17
7.2	Multi-factor authentication (MFA).....	17
7.3	Hosting.....	17
7.4	OWASP checklist review.....	17
7.5	Penetration testing.....	17
8	Solution architecture proposal.....	18
9	Next steps.....	20
10	Bibliography.....	21

1 Executive Summary

This document contains the software requirements specification and informs the software development activities to be completed for the randomised control trial. The specification is built on the high-level requirements submitted as part of deliverable 5.1 and continues to utilise the MoSCoW approach. The iABC platform will be developed iteratively and it is therefore expected that some of the requirements already defined may change as we receive valuable feedback from clinical and patient-group representatives.

We also provide a proposed technical architecture and summary of security activities.

2 Introduction

The software specification document provides a list of lower level iABC requirements built upon the high-level requirements provided in deliverable 5.1. The software specification also includes a proposed technical architecture and security activities.

The specification is built upon the work undertaken in the mAFA II trial (Guo19) and with input from work packages 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 & 7. It is anticipated that new requirements may emerge and that existing requirements may change or are no longer required following the identification of co-morbidities as part of WP2. The agile nature of the development of the iABC means that clinical and patient representative feedback may also modify existing requirements. We continue to use the MoSCoW approach for prioritising each requirement such that any new emerging requirements can be evaluated relative to the existing set.

3 MoSCoW prioritisation

iABC requirements have been classified using the MoSCoW approach and will also be allocated an estimated resource amount which, when combined with the priority of each item, can be used to ensure the iABC platform delivers the highest value requirements. The MoSCoW document will be the source of truth during any requirements discussions and will also be a living document that can be updated as the project progresses.

3.1 Prioritisation

The MoSCoW approach defines each requirement as one of: Must have, Should have, Could have, Won't have.

3.1.1 Must have

These provide the Minimum Usable SubSet (MUST) of requirements which the project guarantees to deliver. These may be classified using at least one of the following:

- If the requirement were not delivered, there would be no point deploying the solution;
- The solution is not legal without it; or
- The solution is unsafe without it.

3.1.2 Should have

Should have requirements can be classified as one of:

- Important, but not vital to the solution;
- May detract from the quality of the solution if excluded, but the solution still works without; or
- A workaround can be put in place that does not require more resource to implement than the requirement itself.

3.1.3 Could have

Could have requirements can be defined as:

- Wanted or desirable, but less important than Should have requirements; or
- Often termed "nice-to-haves".

3.1.4 Won't have

Won't have [this time] requirements are those which the project team has agreed will not be delivered (as part of the current deployment). They are recorded in the high-level requirements document where they help clarify the scope of the project. This avoids them being informally reintroduced later. This also helps to manage expectations that some requirements will simply not make it into the final product, at least not this time around. Won't have requirements can be very powerful in keeping the focus at this point in time on the higher priority items.

3.2 Refining requirements

As AFFIRMO progresses, each high-level requirement will be explored and further defined as a list of low-level requirements. The MoSCoW approach is applied at each level of requirements specification. This method allows the project team to flex the requirements to ensure the resource required and delivery dates remain fixed and is therefore well suited to research projects.

3.3 Determining software output

When planning delivery of software at the project level, it is expected that all Must Have requirements will be delivered, as well as some Should Have and Could Have requirements (if time permits all requirements not marked as Won't Have may be delivered, although this is unusual). Software will be delivered in increments, to facilitate regular feedback from stakeholders. Each increment should also contain a mix of requirement priorities. The inclusion of only Must Have requirements does not provide the software developer(s) with contingency should any unforeseen problems occur.

4 High-level requirements

The high-level requirements document provided in deliverable D5.1 included a list of requirements to be used in the randomised control trial. The requirements were gathered from the work undertaken in the mAFA II trial (Guo19) with input from work packages 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 & 7. From the high-level requirements we have further explored the needs of both clinical and patient users to inform the information contained here and in D5.6. This will inform the software development of the iABC platform.

5 Data model

A key part in understanding the requirements of a digital platform is understanding the data items to be collected. We have defined an initial set of data items to be captured in the iABC platform database (note that this is separate from the eCRF).

5.1 Field specification

For each data item we have defined a proposed data type, identified if this is likely to be a mandatory item, and provided a brief description below.

Category	Item	Type	Mandatory	Description
Prescription	Drug/medication	Text	Y	A field to define the drug or medication being entered.
Prescription	Start date	Date	Y	The date in which a prescription starts
Prescription	End date	Date	Y	The date in which a prescription ends
Prescription	Dosage	Numeric	Y	Specification of how many doses per day should be taken
Prescription	Frequency	Custom		Specification of the frequency with which a drug should be taken e.g. daily, weekly, etc.
Prescription	Notes	Text		Free text field to capture notes from user
Prescription	Date created	Date	Y	Date in which the prescription was created. This will be auto generated and recorded
Prescription	Adherence target	Numeric		A target adherence to prescription. This will enable clinicians to set goals other than 100% if it better suit the patient
Profile	Avatar	Image		An avatar that has been uploaded by the participant if they wish to personalise.

Profile	Colour scheme	Custom		A participant can select from a pre-defined set of colour schemes to personalise their experience.
Profile	Sex at birth	List	Y	Captured at sign-up and limited to Male/Female/Other/prefer not to say
Profile	Age	Numeric	Y	Age only. We will not collect DOB
Profile	Data sharing	Boolean	Y	An option for participants to turn off data sharing with their clinical teams e.g. adherence to prescriptions. Note that this will <u>not</u> remove the data from research datasets.
Profile	Co-morbidities	Custom	Y	For the clinical user to specify the co-morbidities of a patient.
Profile	Centre	Custom		The centre will be a reference to the trial site and will be assigned from a list of pre-defined study centres
Profile	iABC_ID	Custom	Y	This will be auto generated by the platform when a new user is created
Profile	eCRF_ID	Custom	Y	This will be input by the clinician when setting up a patient
Clinical Observation	Time in therapeutic range	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Clinical Observation	BP: Systolic pressure	Numeric		Captured by patient or clinical users to update the platform with BP readings at intervals defined by the clinical team
Clinical Observation	BP: Diastolic pressure	Numeric		

Clinical Observation	Date of clinical obs	Date		Date in which the clinical observation was taken
Clinical Observation	Weight	Numeric		Weight in Kg
Onboarding	Agree to Terms date	Date	Y	Date that the user agreed to items such as End User License Agreement, privacy policy, etc.
Clinical Observation	CHA ₂ DS ₂ -VASc Score	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Clinical Observation	HAD-BLED	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Sleep apnea	Berlin Questionnaire	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Sleep apnea	Epworth sleeping scale	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Sleep apnea	Stop bang score	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Clinical Observation	SAMe-TT2R2	Numeric		This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Alternative healthy eating index	Alternative healthy eating index			This field can be entered by clinical users if needed.
Analytics	Action	Text		Captures actions such as login, page visit, button press, logout
Analytics	Timestamp	Datetime		Datetime stamp to capture analytics action

6 iABC platform requirements

The list of requirements for the iABC platform and their MoSCoW prioritisation are presented below. Some requirements are still to be defined and will be specified following the investigations of WP2 and WP3 – these are excluded from the below.

High-level requirement	Requirement number	Description	Priority
Prescriptions	1.1	As a Clinical user I want to be able to enter/modify/delete* prescription information for participants with the following items: 1. Drug/medication 2. Start date 3. Dosage 4. Frequency 5. End date 6. Notes/comments *"deleting" will mark the item as deleted but will be retained for audit purposes	Must have
	1.2	As a clinical user I want to be able to view a prescriptions summary via a tabular and calendar/graphical summary of medication prescribed over a range (with the option to pick a To and From date via a date picker).	Must have
	1.3	As a participant I want to be able to enter which drugs I've taken such that I can monitor my adherence to prescriptions.	Must have

	1.4	As a clinical user or participant, I want to be able to add annotations to the prescriptions entries that can be seen by the other user (i.e. participant -> clinician or vice versa)	Could have
	1.5	As a user of the system, I want adherence to be displayed in a manner like a traffic light system which gives a clear indication of how closely I adhere to my treatments	Should have
	1.6	As a clinical user I want to be able to set an adherence target that appears as a visual on the prescriptions/adherence view(s).	Could have
Role-based access	3.1	As a system administrator I must ensure roles exist and are secured for data access and display. Roles will include as a minimum: - Participant (intervention arm only) - Interventionist - Researcher - Administrators	Must Have
Translation	4.1	As a user of the system, I want to be able to choose the display language as one of: Spanish, Italian, Bulgarian, Romanian, Danish, Serbian or English.	Must Have
Geriatric usability	5.1	As a user I the iABC platform should be WCAG 2.1 compliant to at least AA standard	Must Have
	5.2	As a participant I want to know participant representatives will provide input to the language used in the iABC platform	Must Have
Education module	7.1	As a clinical user I want to be able to tailor the items available/suggested to participants when adding them to the Affirmo platform.	Should have

	7.2	As a clinical user I want to be able to edit the items available/suggested to participants when adding them to the Affirmo platform.	Should have
	7.3	As a participant I want to be able to view any of the education items included by my clinician on my mobile and desktop/laptop.	Must have
	7.4	As a participant I want to be able to mark items as favourites which then allows me to find the items more quickly.	Could have
	7.5	As a participant I want to be able to search education items for key words to find items easier.	Should have
Click analytics dashboard	8.1	As a researcher I want to be able to access usage information regarding the iABC platform. This will include items such as: 1. Number of participant logins (overall, by region/site, no. logins per participant) 2. Page visits/usage (broken down as above) 3. Participant adherence (measure TBD) 4. Clinician usage	Must have
	8.2	As a clinician I want to be able to access summary usage information regarding the iABC platform for participants in my centre. This will include items such as: 1. Number of participant logins (overall) 2. Page visits/usage (broken down as above) 3. Participant adherence (measure TBD)	Must have
	8.3	As a participant I want to be able to see my own usage history	Could have

Audit	9.1	As a software engineer, I need to be able to investigate bug reports through the use of audit tables. I will need access to the following information: 1. User completing an action 2. Action completed 3. Datetime of action	Must have
	9.2	As a project manager/researcher I need to be provided with audit details should the need arise for any regulatory purposes.	Must have
	9.3	As a software team we need to be able to verify any actions taken in the live data environment to a user/machine level.	Must have
Data analysis	10.1	As a researcher I should be able to download analytics information from the iABC platform in my browser.	Must have
	10.2	As a member of the research team, I should <u>not</u> be provided over email (security concern).	Must have
Web, phone, and tablet compatibility	11.1	As a user I want iABC to be compatible on web, tablet, and mobile devices. Note: We cannot support all devices due to the enormous array of devices on the market but will research and support those devices most commonly used in the target countries. This will include iOS as well as Android-based devices.	Must have
Adherence	12.1	As a researcher I want the iABC to capture participant interaction to facilitate the calculation of adherence to the platform. This may be defined as number of logins, clicks or more specific interaction.	Must have

Participant control	13.1	As a participant I must be able to enable/disable notifications to suit my individual needs	Must have
	13.2	As a participant I should be able to turn off data sharing, which will prevent clinical users from seeing certain data items (details to be confirmed)	Should have
Participant feedback	14.1	As a participant I must have an easy way to provide feedback on the iABC platform via the platform itself.	Must have
	14.2	As a participant I'd like to rate the features/pages I most like.	Could have
Blood pressure monitoring	15.1	As a participant I want to be able to enter blood pressure readings (systolic and diastolic) and view historical results in tabular and graphical format over time.	Must have
	15.2	As a clinician I want to be able to enter blood pressure readings (systolic and diastolic) on behalf of participants and view historical results in tabular and graphical format over time.	Must have
	15.3	As a clinician I want to be able to set reminders (number, frequency, etc.) to prompt participants to enter blood pressure readings.	Should have
	15.4	As a participant I want to be able to turn reminders on/off and have the option to snooze for 10 minutes	Could have
Weight and activity	16.1	As a participant I want to be able to enter my weight/BMI (weight entered in either Kg or St/lb)	Must have

	16.2	As a participant I'd like the iABC platform to utilise native activity tracking information to capture my activity.	Could have
	16.3	As a clinician I want to be able to schedule how regularly the participant needs to complete the physical activity questionnaire (PAQ). I should be able to view the results entered, including any historical results.	Must have
	16.4	As a participant I want to be reminded when to complete the PAQ and see previous entries.	Should have

7 Security

Security forms an integral part of solution design. Below we describe several security features that will be implemented as part of the iABC platform.

7.1 *Vulnerability scans*

The iABC platform (web and mobile) will undergo bi-weekly vulnerability scans. These scans look for any vulnerabilities in the platform and highlight any known risks to the UNIMAN team. Any critical or high risks are addressed immediately.

7.2 *Multi-factor authentication (MFA)*

MFA is required for access to the live study environment for all members of the UNIMAN software development and system administrator teams.

7.3 *Hosting*

iABC will be hosted in a secure public cloud environment within the EU. The hosting provider will provide an ISO27001 certified environment for the duration of the programme.

7.4 *OWASP checklist review*

A full OWASP (<https://owasp.org/>) checklist review will be performed against the iABC platform before deploying for use by participants. This widely accepted standard provides guidance on current security threats. The checklist review will output a series of recommendations for improving security. Each will be reviewed by the UNIMAN and implemented where appropriate.

7.5 *Penetration testing*

External penetration testing will be performed on the iABC platform during the study. This provides external input with regards to the security of the platform and highlights any weaknesses that may need to be addressed.

8 Solution architecture proposal

Below is a proposed solution architecture for the AFFIRMO platform.

UNIMAN = University of Manchester
 AWS = Amazon Web Service
 TLS = Transport layer security

9 Next steps

The requirements for the iABC will continue to evolve. WP5 will work with WP2, 3, 6 & 7 to further define the low-level requirements of the iABC platform. Software development begins in M13 and will be ready for the RCT in M24.

10 Bibliography

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